

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE DEVELOPMENT OF TERMINOLOGY AFTER THE 40S IN ALBANIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to treat and highlight one of the ways that has been followed for the enrichment of the terminology in the Albanian language. This lexicon has been enriched by using different linguistic tools such as linguistic calques, composites, derived words, neologisms. The methodology used is analytical, analyzing derived words based on grammatical categories.

Keywords: derived word, lexicon of the Albanian language, borrowings, lexicon of mechanics

Introduction

In contrast to general language, terminology requires regular proportions in the same amount of terms and concepts in the terminological lexicon. In this context, the purifying process must maintain the correct understanding of the concept - term rather than the lexical sign. According to Duro A. (1995), if the meaning of the general word can vary with synonyms, the concept expressed by the term in Albanian should be given only with a sign or the synonyms should be absolute synonyms.

One of the main characteristics of the mechanics lexicon for example is the diverse use of suffixes for derived formations, which has been conditioned by the tendency to cover technical concepts with Albanian words as well as by the attempt to differentiate different concepts on the linguistic level.

Duro (1995) distinguishes six groups of important factors for the pronunciation of Albanian terminology:

- 1) Intra-terminological factors.
- 2) Extra-terminological factors.
- 3) Inter-terminological factors.
- 4) Historical factors.
- 5) Social and political factors.

6) Organizational - planning factors are a logical consequence of the influence on them of social and political factors, of language policy in the field of terminology. They are closely related to the treatment of terminology as a practical social activity, where organized and planned work by the organisms that deal with it occupies an important place. So here it is necessary to establish the relevant structures to create a terminological data bank and the drafting of terminological dictionaries.

In this field there are many studies by Albanian researchers such as Dodbiba L. (1972), Samara M. (1972), Papa A, Leka F (1988), Sima K., Keta B (1989) Cipuri H. (1989) etc. .

Results and discussion

Relying on the existing models of word formation in the Albanian language, many nouns, adjectives and verbs and less adverbs have been built in this lexicon through derivation.

We will analyze the derived words according to the grammatical categories they represent:

Noun

Derived formations Noun+Noun

These formations are mainly based on the relationships that exist between the derived noun and the basic noun form itself. A prominent place in these derived formations is occupied by the relationship of diminution, for the expression of which the elements such as *th - topth* (Eng. *ball*), *nyjth* (Eng. *knot*), etc. *zë- urëzë, kokërrzë, dorzë, gjuhëzë, sharrzë, gojëz, thikëzë, fyellzë, arkëzë* (Eng. *bridge, grain, hand, tongue, saw, mouth, knife, flute, crate*) etc.; *kë*, for example, *rrotkë, unazkë, govatkë* (Eng. *wheels, rings, washtub*), etc. Many formations are realized based on the relationship between the object represented by the basic noun form and the place or device expressed by the derived form, in which this object functions, in this case the suffix *or; tor* for example: *avulllore, farkore, fjetore, kullestore, vizatore, zjarrtore, tymore* (*steamer, forge, threader, colander, workers, drafters, furnace*), etc. served here. Another relationship encountered in many derived noun formations is that between the object and its producer or user. To realize this type of relationship, have served the suffix like *ar*, for example, *tajar, timonar, tymtar, kthistar, hekurtar, furrëtar* (Eng. *carpenter, a helmsman, a smoker, a turner, an ironworker, a baker*) etc.; *xhi* such as *motorxhi, teneqexhi, kazanxhi, kallaxhi* (Eng. *motorcyclist, tinsmith, boilermaker, tinker*) etc.; The suffixes *inë, isht* are mainly used to realize the relationship between the object and its remains, such as *limurinë, hekurishte, hekurinë, qelqurinë* etc.

The relationship between the object and its condition is expressed by means of suffixes that appear productively in formations such as *dellsi*, *vishkullsi*, *rrafshësi*, *zjarrësi*, *ndryshkësi*, *largësi* etc. The object in these formations is represented by the nominal productive subject.

To express some technical concepts, words from the general lexicon of the language have been used, which have been modified by being equipped with additional elements, for example, the element *(ë)s* has been added to a few words with general use to differentiate these from their use special, for example *tymsi*, *hovsi*, *gishtsi* etc. This element appears quite productive for the formation of nouns derived from the nominal subject.

Derived Verb+Noun formations

For the formation of the names of this group, a number of suffixes with a more or less specialized meaning are used, for example *(m)je* and *im* for the process of action, such as *rrëshqitme*, *ndemje*, *kalitme*, *ngru\imja*, *tretje*, *presje*, *merentim*, *trazim* etc. (Eng. *sliding*, *stirring*, *tempering*, *freezing*, *digestion* etc.); *esë* for the result of the action such as *shkëlqesë*, *meremetesë*, *gërresë* etc. *(ë)* as without the condition as *bartësi*, *ngritësi*, *përkulesë*, *depërtsi*, *përshkrimsi* etc. (Eng. *carrier*, *lifter*, *bending*, *penetration*, *description*, etc.) / *ore* or *tore* for the place where the implied action is performed in the verbal subject, e.g. *dredhtore*, *shkrinjëtore*, *kullore* etc.

Some other suffixes are used to form verb nouns or that mark the tool that performs the action of the verbal subject, for example, *dëftak*, *dëftues*, *përdasi*, *mbështjellësa*, *këthyes*, *kollojse*, *notues*, *fluturonjës*, *ngrehse* etc.

Most of these nouns are formed based on an indeterminable verb such as *notues*, *shkelsor*, *kollorë* etc. The rest are formations whose origin is motivated according to the structure (Noun Verb) Noun, so they are realized on a noun subject. Here are introduced the formations with the suffixes like *im sheshim*, *gëlqerim*, *pikëzim*, *prodhim*, *kryqëzim*, *qëndrim* etc.; *ues* as *pluhurues*, *birues*, *shenjues*, *rregullues*, *depozitues* etc.; *onjës* *trajtonjës*, *daltonjës* etc.; *osës* *vijosës* etc. The third subgroup consists of terms that express the initial concept with an adjectival term, such as *drejtues*, *shtremsinat*, *rrallim* etc.

Derived formations Adjective+Noun

A good number of these formations are realized based on a non-motivative adjectival subject, mainly marking the state or property of the corresponding adjective. Here are entered the formations with *(ë)si* such as *ftohtësi*, *matësi*, *shtangësi*, *tërthorësi*, *gjanësi*, *gjatësi*, *plotësi*, *ngurtësi*, *rendësi*, *pingulsi* etc. (Eng. *coldness*, *measure*, *heaviness*, *transversality*, *similarity*, *length*, *fullness*, *hardness*, *importance*, *perpendicularity*), etc.

The second group consists of formations with structure (Verb+Noun)Noun, that is, the initial concept is represented by a verbal subject as the basic forms of these formations such as *ndjenjëshmësi*, *qëndrueshmësi*

etc. (Eng. *emotionality*, *stability*), etc. The third group consists of terms with the structure (Noun+Adjective)Noun where the initial concept is expressed with a name such as *llastikësi*, *qartësi* etc. (Eng. *elasticity*, *clarity*), etc. For the formation of derived nouns in the lexicon of mechanics in this period, the suffixes *im*, *je*, *as*, *or*, *tor*, *ues* are the most popular.

Adjective

Derived formation Noun+Adjective

The main suffixes that serve to form compound adjectives with a noun base are *or* such as *hekuror*, *lëndor*, *pluhuror*, *qelqor* (Eng. *iron*, *materially*, *dusty*, *glassy*), etc.; *shëm* like, for example, *brylshëm*, *i pjatshëm*, *i ajrshëm*, *i paralelshëm*, *i yndyrshëm*, *i ujshëm*, *i magnetshëm* etc.; *at-ak* such as *fluturak*, *lojtak*, *pluhnak*, *veshtullak* etc.; *ues* such as *pjatues*, *konus* etc.; *(ë)se* such as *ujse*, *zjarrse*, *motorëse*, *thëngjillëse* etc.; *ik-* *magnetik*, *metalik* etc.;

Derived formation Verb+Adjective

Derived adjectives formed from verbs are divided into three groups:

- Adjectives in which the initial concept is represented by a noun such as *e dhëmbëzues-e*, *të forcues-e*, *frenues*, *e fuqizues-e*, *transmissionues-e*, *të kallajisura*, *i kokrrizum* etc. In general, the suffix *ues-e* is used in an active sense, that is, the qualified object performs the action implied by the productive subject of the adjective, e.g. *inhibitory*, but in some cases this suffix is used with different modifying meanings, such as in the formations (note) *shkallëzuese*, *dhëmbëzues*, *cilindruese*, *lakuese* etc.

- Adjectives in which the initial concept is represented by a verb, e.g. *i ngritshëm*, *i depërtueshëm*, *depërtues*, *i djegshëm*, *i rrëshqitshëm*, *rrëshqitës*, *rrjedhës*, *i rrjedhshëm*, *veçuese*, *i tretshëm* etc. (Eng. *elevating*, *permeable*, *penetrating*, *combustible*, *slippery*, *sliding*, *flowing*, *flowing*, *separating*, *soluble*), etc.

- Adjectives in which the initial concept is expressed by an adjective, as in the case of *te vjetëruar*, *I praktikueshem* etc., (*outdated material*, *practicable*), etc.

Derived formations Adjective+Adjective

Both the adjective representing the initial concept and the derived adjective formed with the help of the adverbial element mark the same concept, so the suffix here conceptually represents a pleonastic element, for example *elektrikore*, *i normalshëm*, *i automatikshëm*, *i paralelshëm* etc.

Verb

Derived formations Noun+Verb

The relationships that exist in these formations between the basic noun subject and the derived verbal form are among the most diverse, based on which these resulting concepts are motivated as:

- Return something in the form or state of the object represented by the noun subject, for *çelikos*, *dhëmbëzonz*, *sheshoj*, etc.

- To wear something with the metal of the object represented by the noun subject, such as *remtue*, *me zinkue*, *celikonj* etc.

- To work something by means of the object expressed by the noun subject, for example *daltue, tajue, trinue*, etc.

Derived formations Adjective+Verb

The formations of this group are few, where you can mention *ngurtoj, naltosej*, etc.

Adverb

Verb-derived formations can be divided into two groups:

Those that are formed on a noun subject.

Those that are formed on an adjectival subject, for example automatically, hermetically, technically, indirectly, etc.

Among these formations are also some derived adverbs of the noun type (**i sht**), the use of which was limited within that period.

Conclusions

Terminology, as an interdisciplinary science that studies the formation and systematization of concepts of different fields of science and technology, has as its main object the concept and the term. It uses the concepts that it borrows from some other fields such as logic, information, etc. to implement its terminological analysis, which differs from linguistic analysis. The latter can be word formation analysis, semantic analysis, syntactic analysis, etc. while the terminological analysis consists in the identification of concepts and the definition of relationships between concepts based on which the construction of the conceptual system in a certain subject area is realized.

Starting from the linguistic point of view, any sound form that expresses a lexical meaning is treated as a word and is subject to linguistic laws both in terms of expression and content. While starting from the terminological point of view, every sound form representing a concept is treated as a term and is subject to certain terminological laws both in terms of expression and content.

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